

CURRENT METHODOLOGICAL TECHNIQUES FOR ENHANCING STUDENTS' ACADEMIC WRITING SKILLS

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Abstract:

Academic writing is a multifaceted phenomenon that encompasses the production of written documents (theses, abstracts, articles) as well as oral reports, presentations, and other written works. These are created with consideration for the demands of argumentation, the use of specific discursive markers and metalanguage, as well as other formal elements that define the scientific style.

Key words: plagiarism, scientific style, academic writing, English for Academic Purposes, and professional ability, online tools.

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Any field of human activity related to business, professional, and scientific discourse requires written communication which plays a crucial role in the development of a scientist's linguistic personality. One of the key requirement characteristics that sets a specialist in any academic area is the possession of academic writing skills.

During the process of a scientific work writing, consideration is given to the outline of its constituent parts, i.e., composition and paragraphing, stylistically justified methods of cohesiveness and coherence, linguistic compliance with structural design, and written etiquette conventions. The extent to which the level of difficulty is identified, the similar complexity of vocabulary and grammatical structures should be considered. The essential focus should be oriented toward developing academic topic vocabulary, acquiring information on a variety of genres, and teaching criteria used in academic discourse.

Various academic fields necessitate the construction of academic writing skills, leading to an integration of practical instructions in the teaching process. Developing students' intercultural communication abilities is one of the goals of learning some disciplines at the bachelor's level of study. To exemplify, the EAP (English for Academic Purposes) course, sets the aims of developing students' scientific style awareness and competence construction in all its variants. One of the main goals of the EAP course is to improve students' ability to read academic texts, authentic literary texts and write well in an official style. Therefore, teaching academic writing in English involves not only familiarizing students with its vocabulary but also with its compositional structure and stylistic elements, though some of the students' challenges related to these features deal with a lot of academic writing components, templates, clichés, and collocations.

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Implementing teaching academic writing is also necessary especially when it comes to the students' employment, so that the learning process should be oriented towards practice, and integration into global processes. These matters may serve as a strong motivator to focus more thoroughly on the techniques of academic writing instruction. Students must participate in international educational programs in order to be integrated into international processes. Students should also be capable to access appropriate web resources and write, following the academic writing style. As an example, Grammarly app may be used for academic purposes by looking at the letter verification bot analysis. It can provide students with advanced-level phrases that are not part of their active vocabulary.

Students can be taught a set of strategies and techniques on the ways to avoid plagiarism while examining and evaluating their written drafts. Some online services checking text for plagiarism, such as Plagiarism or Plagtracker may also be provided. These tools help students reflect on the text and raise their level of language awareness both in a foreign (L2) and native (L2) languages.

In higher education the Web of Science and Scopus databases can also be used as storage of academic scientific publications. Moreover, students can study the structure of an academic paper, become familiar with scientific terminology and the ways of successful organization of cohesive text, and other world standards in academic writing domain.

Writing course aimed at developing academic and writing skills should be designed according to the modern innovative methodology which in its turn will provide a number of possible instructional variations on writing academic articles. Furthermore, the instructional material should be properly selected for teaching fundamentals of successful writing competences:

- composition of an English letter
- essay writing
- taking notes during lectures
- carrying out research

Academic writing requires more than just using linguistic knowledge, it also deals with text outline, maintaining cohesion and coherence within the text, providing quotations and paraphrasing following APA-citation style, analyzing the data, searching for new information through the Internet resources, exploring the database of some online contemporary tools, etc. However, not every strategy suggested can be applied to every kind of academic writing. For the most time, the methods can be used when working with texts, and even more so when creating presentations.

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